

Supplemental Information 1: Repository Resilience Project Survey Questions

About this Resource

This supplement includes survey questions used for the project associated with Sutton-Kennedy, T., Crall, A., Trice, A., & Gum, J. (2026). *Repository Resilience in Practice: Findings and Strategies from a Community in Crisis*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20617197>.

Introduction

Thanks for your interest in the Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS) project, funded by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. This survey is intended to collect information to better understand the real-world impacts of data access disruptions and to inform actionable strategies for building repository resilience during periods of crisis.

Please note that we are collecting and processing data collected through this survey in accordance with the project's [Data Privacy Policy](#). We are not collecting any personal data through this form. Therefore, if you have general interest in the project and would like to receive relevant communications on project findings and other relevant information, you can sign up via our interest form.

If you have any questions or concerns about the survey, please contact the project team at rcs@esipfed.org.

1. How would you identify yourself as it relates to this project? Please check all that apply.

- User of data housed in a repository: I deposit and/or access and use data stored in repositories for my work or research.
- Administrator or manager of a data repository: I oversee repository operations, policies, staffing, or strategic direction.

- Scientific and technical staff at a data repository: I contribute to the day-to-day operation, curation, or maintenance of a repository.
- Citizen Archivist: I help to identify, collect, and archive data from public repositories.

Logic: If “user of data housed in a repository” selected in [1]

2. What type of data user are you? Please check all that apply.

- Research and Academic Users: data are used to advance knowledge, conduct analyses, validate or replicate studies, develop new methods or models.
- Policy and Decision-Making Users: data are used for evidence-based policy, impact assessment, and public accountability.
- Operational and Crisis Response Users: data are used for rapid situational awareness, response coordination, and risk forecasting.
- Private Sector and Industry Users: data are used by businesses and consultancies for product development, market analysis, compliance, and competitive intelligence.
- Nonprofit, Advocacy, and Media Users: data are used for storytelling, transparency, accountability, and public engagement.
- Repository and Infrastructure Professional Users: data are used to ensure data quality, interoperability, preservation, and discoverability.
- Community and Local Knowledge Users: data are used for place-based decision making, resource management, and cultural preservation.
- Other

Data Disruption and Loss

3. Have you ever experienced a disruption in data access?*

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

Logic: If yes to [3]

4. What was the cause of the disruption(s) you experienced?

Long answer

Logic: If yes to [3]

5. Which of the following impacts were caused by the disruption(s)? Check all that apply.

- Economic or financial loss
- Operational disruptions / disruption in work
- Delayed decision-making
- Compromised public safety and disaster response
- Disruption in research
- Reputational damage or erosion of trust

- Increased inequity or exclusion
- Loss of institutional memory or historical record
- Inhibited innovation or economic growth
- Increased misinformation and reduced accountability
- Longer term societal and environmental costs
- None of the above

Logic: With exception of “None of the above” to [5]

6. What was the severity of each impact you selected? Please rank on a scale from 1 (no impact) to 5 (severe impact).

Likert scale piped in from previous responses

Logic: If yes to [3]

7. Are there additional impacts you have experienced or observed from a disruption in data access that were not included in the list displayed previously?

Impacts included: Economic or financial loss, Operational disruptions / disruption in work, Delayed decision-making, Compromised public safety or disaster response, Disruption in research, Reputational damage or erosion of trust, Increased inequity or exclusion, Loss of institutional memory or historical record, Inhibited innovation or economic growth, Increased misinformation or reduced accountability, Longer term societal or environmental costs

Long answer

Loss of Paid Staff

8. From your experience, has the loss of paid staff played a role in the disruption or recovery process?*

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

Logic: If yes to [8]

9. Which of the following impacts to data access were caused by the loss of paid staff?

Please check all that apply.

- Breakdown of data quality and integrity
- Interrupted repository operations
- Loss of institutional knowledge and continuity
- Reduced compliance with data policies and standards
- Decreased user support and community engagement
- Delayed or failed system upgrades
- Erosion of trust and reputation
- Reduced innovation and adaptability

- Long-term sustainability risks
- None of the above

Logic: With exception of “None of the above” to [9]

10. What was the severity of each impact you selected? Please rank on a scale from 1 (no impact) to 5 (severe impact).

Likert scale piped in from previous responses

Logic: If yes to [8]

11. Are there additional impacts you have experienced or observed from a disruption in data access that were not included in the list displayed previously?

Impacts included: Breakdown of data quality and integrity, Interrupted repository operations, Loss of institutional knowledge and continuity, Reduced compliance with data policies and standards, Decreased user support and community engagement, Delayed or failed system upgrades, Erosion of trust and reputation, Reduced innovation and adaptability, Long-term sustainability risks

Long answer

Mitigation Strategies for Repository Resilience

Logic: If yes to [3]

12. Which mitigation strategies were in place prior to or during disruptions in data access? Please check all that apply.

- Redundant and distributed data infrastructure
- Comprehensive documentation and metadata standards
- Succession planning and cross-training of personnel
- Automated quality assurance and compliance tools
- Transparent governance and incident response policies
- Open, interoperable, and accessible data standards
- Community and stakeholder engagement
- Equity and accessibility measures
- Sustainable funding
- Institutional partnerships
- Innovation and continuous improvement culture
- None of the above

Logic: With exception of “None of the above” to [12]

13. How effective were the mitigation strategies you selected that were in place prior to or during disruptions in data access? Please rank on a scale from 1 (not at all effective) to 5 (extremely effective).

Likert scale piped in from previous responses

Logic: If yes to [3]

14. Are there additional impacts you have experienced or observed from a disruption in data access that were not included in the list displayed previously?

Mitigation strategies included: Redundant and distributed data infrastructure, Comprehensive documentation and metadata standards, Succession planning and cross-training of personnel, Automated quality assurance and compliance tools, Transparent governance and incident response policies, Open / interoperable / and accessible data standards, Community and stakeholder engagement, Equity and accessibility measures, Sustainable funding, Institutional partnerships, Innovation and continuous improvement culture

Long answer

15. From your experience, please rank how important the following mitigation strategies are for ensuring the long-term resilience of data repositories and the communities that maintain them. Please rank on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (extremely important).

- Redundant and distributed data infrastructure
- Comprehensive documentation and metadata standards
- Succession planning and cross-training of personnel
- Automated quality assurance and compliance tools
- Transparent governance and incident response policies
- Open, interoperable, and accessible data standards
- Community and stakeholder engagement
- Equity and accessibility measures
- Sustainable funding
- Institutional partnerships
- Innovation and continuous improvement culture

16. What additional practices, tools or policies do you think are required to help you or your organization prepare for future disruptions in data access?

Long answer

Ending

Please provide any additional comments relevant to this survey.

Thank you for sharing your experiences and recommendations with us.

As noted previously, we are not collecting any personal data through this survey. Therefore, if you have general interest in the project and would like to receive relevant communications on project findings and other relevant information, you can [sign up via our interest form](#).

If you have any questions or concerns about the survey or would be interested in participating in a related focus group, please contact the project team at rcs@esipfed.org.